

Organizational Outcome Priorities of bonding the Individuals to Teamwork.

Author's Details: ⁽¹⁾ Dr Syed Muneer Ahmed Shah ⁽²⁾ Mr Shoaib Hyder ⁽³⁾ Ms Safia Khan

⁽¹⁾ Associate Professor, ^(2,3) MS Scholar Department of Business Administration, Shah Abdul Latif University, Khairpur Mirs, Pakistan

ABSTRACT

Strategic management dimensions of the firms are in a continuous shift from the one to the other as per the changing tunes of time. Organizations have been searching for the measurement parameters that better describes the outcome priorities of a proposed project, so that the bonding of individuals (forming teamwork) may be effective and productive, avoiding the failure of cost of investment in the team formation and structure. The study engages four highly correlated independent variables (total quality perspective, individual learning & training, inspiring organizational challenges and effective decision making) to the dependent variable (Teamwork). The aim of the study was to sum up all teamwork outcomes and suggest for better outcome option(s) to working teams around, to commit the work as per the significance of the factor(s). A sample of 176 Engineers, working or worked in discrete teams from private and public sector was considered. The hypotheses formed are held true and there exists a significant correlation between the four independent variables to the dependent variable. PASW Statistics-18 was used to get the results with application of Linear Regression, by the help of principle components analysis (based on eigenvalue) for data analysis and interpretation of results. It is found that each of the independent variable extracted by the statistical software was completely compatible to the proposed model of the research and suggests that organizations are promoting the outcome of individual learning & training at first (81%), total quality perspective at second (78%), inspiring organizational challenges at third (74%) and finally effective decision making (65%) in bonding the individuals (teamwork).

KEYWORDS: Teamwork, Organizational Outcomes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The growing competitive pressures of economics and technology, on personnel management is a red-hot issue worldwide, for how to achieve individual motivation, job commitment and high involvement at work place, puts the Organizations towards changing their strategic dimensions time to time, for outcome priorities of proposed projects, by bonding the individuals (teamwork), so that workload may be distributed in a sense of involving discrete professionals to achieve one goal in a prescribed limit of time. Tohidi (2011), found that the formation of cross functional teams in an organization promotes shared responsibility and a sound working environment too.

Forming a team is to bring role dynamics on a workplace (changing aspects of individual's work) creates sometimes positive (human feels promoted and good) and at other times negative effect (results in role ambiguity/role conflict), as per human acceptance of team introduction. Therefore a multi-range of factor(s) should be kept in consideration in order to promote teamwork; like team structure (internal/external), rewards, outcomes, costs, benefits and even the consequences as a whole, because they all could affect seriously the organizational setting.

This is how; the research is centric to themes of inquiring how organizational priorities are formed as per the factor consideration; when it involves a professionally-differentiated/similar workforce (teamwork) to create a scientific pool of talent. No doubt, everyone knows that organizations are headed and supported by teams (like board of directors for decision making, review & audit committee for better profitability, Compliance committee to ensure quality perspectives, HR committee to recruit, hire, train and motivate individuals and others). But let us see here, why the teams are formed (outcome priorities) at frontlines for project handling and trouble solving.

The literature recommends several elements to be discussed, when teamwork is promoted; but this article focuses on four outcome dimensions of teamwork: *Total Quality Perspective* (to ensure the quality conformance to planned outcome), *Individual Learning & Training* (to ensure employee skill development to better achieve competitive work outcome), *Inspiring Organizational Challenges* (to comply with 360 focus on ongoing market share contests and its outcome), *Effective Decision Making* (to safeguard organizational future by selecting a right option at the spur of the movement).

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Moorhead & Griffin - Constructing a line of assistance in an organization is to form the teamwork by a scientific way. The need is to determine the reasons for why and how the teams may be formed, would it be a better option to bring about excellence in teamwork outcome or rather it may be opt out. The successful team building has its roots in determining organizational goals, analyzing work related performance, focusing on scope of decision making and considering relationship among working individuals; and it would be more better to ponder on all, prior to bonding the individuals to work together.

Luca & Tarricone (2001) - A case study research, based on the principles of learning the methodology of project management in an institution for the software programmers, who possess intangible set of skill and needs to build their mental maps as per the growing needs of online client system, whereby the topology of discrete functions is the core subject in the field of emotional intelligence for computer sciences students and engineers. The results put forward and highlight different issues of solving the multidimensional problems via increasing communication electronic networks, having a collaborative virtual environment that tends to refresh the programmers interpersonal and social set of skills to boost their intelligence level. For the described situations is a one solution that best meets the needs assessment of individual skills building and is pioneered to the roots of team working that provides synergic outcomes, involving a bundle of talent acquisitions.

Andrews (2002) - Teamwork in multinationals, public and private organizations is promoted to come up with smart solutions to complex problems. Knowing the outcome dimension would better suggest improving the investment cost of teamwork formation that turns the simple outcome to synergic outcome of the team formed. Technological houses ensure to bond the individuals by means of virtual and innovation; whereby the investment is done to make people learn better, boost technological advancement and improve processes, that finally provided a sustainable advantage to the IT houses. The team bonding must be compatible to the firm size; if it is too high then it is a very good sign to involve a scientific talent pool to avoid the time conflict array; but if the firm size is small, no need to bond the individual and waste the resources.

Adenfelt & Lagerstrom (2006) - Creation of the knowledge circle in an MNC today is a need based factor of good employment. Projects are to be proposed for the introduction of an idea into a product, improving the cycle of process or providing a solution to a strategic business system. The study is based on the case study; it is found that it is completely a challenge for the multinationals to perform transnational projects, whereby the community and technical persons are involved, for knowledge sharing and creation to win the game of being the enabler to better understand the corporate culture and build the trust for the same.

A. Marin & Martinez (2007) - If an organization wants to become a learning organization, it needs to change its dimensions of data management to savvy management; it is not possible by one man show, it is all around by bonding the individuals (teamwork). Knowledge management suggests that teamwork is built to insist the team members to "do more" as per rules of total quality, whereby the process improvement is needed and control of workload is divided to enhance speed of business functions. Teamwork in perspectives of knowledge management is proved to be a catalyst: that triggers competency, backup behavioral support, mutual performance monitoring and shared problems, to overcome.

Jiang (2010) - The maximization of team (formed in different structures) performance needs different kinds of rewards, as per the encouragement assessment by employers, to achieve operational success of their work plan. Competitive trials have been the ongoing analysis tools for setting the teams to work on any assignment, in multinational firms rather than to go on individually. No doubt, the reason of team formation promotes staff development, rapid attainment of company objectives and builds a social relation among the working individuals to form organizational culture and community.

Shagholi, Hussin, Siraj, Zahra Naimie, Assadzadeh, & Moayedi (2010) - The research reveals that organizational trust, in eyes of the employee, has been found as the basis of building employee confidence and assignment of proper responsibility to them for being in the organizational position. Whereby, the said employee displays a voluntary and cooperative behavior regarding formal decision making, assigned to the employee that ultimately supports the creation of fresh ideas with the project productivity, forming a circle of improved performance dimension at all.

Tohidi (2011) - Ensuring the effectiveness and productivity of the cross-functional teams require shared role task and responsibility for the contribution of talent donation in the specific pool of expertise; this is all possible by the good manifesto of cost reward and effort recognition system that ultimately will bring about the perspectives of education and leadership to old employees and guidance for the newly involved personnel, but it must be subject to the soundness of team size and structure, members behavior acceptance and motivation for task assignment and triggering the IT based working in an organization, so that the performance measurement dimensions may be defined for outcome parameters.

Kashefi, Ismail, & Yusof (2012) - The study is bonded with the identification and learning of core engineering subject that is multivariable calculus (with its behavioral applications), in order to improve the generic skills of engineers in their academic life, so as to boost their performance in their professional life. It was found that there exists a learning gap for establishing interpersonal talent portfolio for engineers, for building the teamwork and communication array of engineers; however, the study suggests that all of the engineers were quite agree to the view that learning is completely based on having the help of instructors in the engineering projects.

Carmenado, Rodríguez, & Gajardo (2012) - The study has been carried out in an educational institution to know how the personal and interpersonal skills are acquired and being developed, based on the project participative learning; whereby the value of academic and professional awareness and background is of utmost importance so that the lesser cost of adjustment may be invested in forming teamwork. It is all about sharing responsibility, promoting leadership and learning about negotiation, so as to form the behavioral competency in individual personality. The results of research intend to point out the assessment dimensions and development of

competence in relative, scientific and behavioral traits of working in project management. Striving student, who meets the deadlines would ensure the keen of learning in their skill improvement and fast track learning.

Bektas & Sohrabifard (2013) - The functional outcome of forming the teamwork is to empower the participating employees, for improving the state of organizational productivity, situation solving capability and information sharing behavior. Stepping ahead, research suggests that the teams, which have more knowledge and skills, communication network, trust among team members and good incentive plan, would eminently foster employee state of empowerment in betterment of performing formal roles and responsibilities at work place.

Stefanovski & Bock (2013) - Coping together the individuals, with a diversified talent ensures the joint learning, which in return, provides a significant change in performance outcome for teamwork. A proposed model for understanding, is used in a sense that an individual player was put in against of expert player in a game, whereby he lost; while at the same, a team was put in against of expert player and the results seen were quite different and encouraging for building teamwork, thereby learning begins to change its state, for every team member in a joint learning.

Muneer, Iqbal, Khan, & Long (2014) - Organizations have been trying to build the perceived organization support and organizational trust, in the eyes of its employees to generate their job commitment timeline, in order to prescribe an influential dimension of knowledge-sharing behavior by them in their surroundings for organizational image promotion and development. The work reveals that working on trends of successful knowledge managing and knowledge spreading initiatives require a proper compensation plan for leading managers to provide essential support for inspiring sharing behavior among their team associates, so that all participants can learn via effective teamwork.

Gulatee & Masek (2014) - The study is centric to the standards of knowing about the fact of forming the group assignments by linking variety of individuals in the large software houses, as it is completely beyond the ability of a single person and possible with the formation of a teamwork. The study is conceded in an institution to provide the students with an opportunity to find better colleagues for their final year project assignment. It was concluded that introducing the lines of team culture is more important to be understood by an individual rather than the understanding of organizational culture, as a person will have to work among the other persons for professional enhancement.

3. RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

To sum up all teamwork outcomes and suggest for better outcome option(s) to working teams around, to commit the work as per the significance of the factor(s).

4. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

- H1: The Outcome of Total quality perspective is highly correlated to the Teamwork.*
- H2: The Outcome of Individual learning & Training is significantly correlated to the Teamwork.*
- H3: The Outcome of Inspiring Organizational Challenges is simply correlated to the Teamwork.*
- H4: The Outcome of Effective Decision Making is highly correlated to the Teamwork.*

5. PROPOSED RESEARCH MODEL

6. METHODOLOGY

6.1 Data Collection Technique

Primary source of data collection was considered meaningful, in order to gather the information by distributing a set of questionnaires, involving 33 items; 03 items for demographics (gender, age group and qualification) and remaining 30 were embarked to close ended responses utilizing five-point Likert scale (1: Strongly Disagree, 2: Disagree, 3: Neutral, 4: Agree, 5: Strongly Agree). Secondary source of data was also collected by reviewing different publications to quote the work of other authors related to this study.

6.2 Sampling

The study is based on random selection sampling for 176 respondents; whereby the participants were all engineers, either working in different projects or had worked earlier in any engineering project from private and public sector.

6.3 Quantitative Technique

Step-1: The reliability of instrument was analyzed by using PASW Statistics-18.

Step-2: Principal components analysis (based on eigenvalue) was made for data reduction and factor formation.

Step-3: Linear Regression was applied for correlation results/values between independent and dependent variable(s).

6.4 Diagnostic Test

$$TW = \alpha + TQP\beta_1 + ILT\beta_2 + IOC\beta_3 + EDM\beta_4 + \mu$$

7. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

7.1 Reliability Analysis

The instrument reliability was measured by two different techniques; first was the cumulative measurement and the next was factor-wise measurement of Cronbach’s alpha. The analysis proposes that the items contain good and accurate approximation of correlation values that tends to construct a good compatibility of involved variables to the corresponding research topic. Furthermore, it is found very much meaningful by the results estimation of individual factor loading of Cronbach’s alpha, which is almost found greater than 0.7 for each variable. (Table-1)

<i>Table-1</i>		
<i>Reliability Analysis (Cumulative & Factor-wise)</i>		
	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
<i>Total (Cumulative)</i>	0.949	30
<i>Total Quality Perspective</i>	0.801	07
<i>Individual Learning & Training</i>	0.778	05
<i>Inspiring Organizational Challenges</i>	0.721	04
<i>Effective Decision Making</i>	0.773	04
<i>Teamwork</i>	0.888	10

7.2 Components Matrix

Table-2

Components Matrix					
No of Items	Factor-wise				
	Total Quality Perspective	Individual Learning & Training	Inspiring Organizational Challenges	Effective Decision Making	Teamwork
01	0.635	0.756	0.700	0.810	0.656
02	0.636	0.758	0.770	0.845	0.703
03	0.655	0.704	0.725	0.845	0.741
04	0.765	0.734	0.759	0.564	0.638
05	0.680	0.687	-----	-----	0.701
06	0.698	-----	-----	-----	0.760
07	0.658	-----	-----	-----	0.719
08	-----	-----	-----	-----	0.705
09	-----	-----	-----	-----	0.728
10	-----	-----	-----	-----	0.726
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)	0.855	0.813	0.739	0.740	0.908
Eigenvalue (% of Variance)	45.798	53.064	54.640	60.058	50.215

The component matrix shows the values of individual factor loading for the items being involved for that variable in the research data collection and response; it is clearly shown by the analysis that the each factor item(s) value is ranging from 0.564 (being lowest) to 0.845 (highest), except item no 04 in EDM factor, each item contains greater value than 0.60, which suggests the good and responsible responses by the respondents. (Table-2). Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) for sample adequacy for each of the variable involved is greater than 0.70 and sounds good fit for the data competence and results, with the level of variance being individually involved factor wise to predict the variance of responses in data. (Table-2)

7.3 Scree Plot

Scree plot for each factor has been given here to observe the eigenvalues (variance proportion) for each factor, associated with research data collected to better ensure the reviewer assessment of where the most of the variability in the data is explained.

7.4 Correlations

Table-3

Correlations						
		<i>Teamwork</i>	<i>Total Quality Perspective</i>	<i>Individual Learning & Training</i>	<i>Inspiring Organizational Challenges</i>	<i>Effective Decision Making</i>
Pearson Correlation	<i>Teamwork</i>	1.000	0.778	0.812	0.743	0.651
	<i>Total Quality Perspective</i>	0.778	1.000	0.764	0.748	0.574
	<i>Individual Learning & Training</i>	0.812	0.764	1.000	0.713	0.592
	<i>Inspiring Organizational Challenges</i>	0.743	0.748	0.713	1.000	0.548
	<i>Effective Decision Making</i>	0.651	0.574	0.592	0.548	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	<i>Teamwork</i>	-----	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000
	<i>Total Quality Perspective</i>	0.000	-----	0.000	0.000	0.000
	<i>Individual Learning & Training</i>	0.000	0.000	-----	0.000	0.000
	<i>Inspiring Organizational Challenges</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	-----	0.000
	<i>Effective Decision Making</i>	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	-----

The statistical relationship of model for the measurement of dependence value between the proposed variables have been found a good fit with the significance value of 0.000, for each variable. The model is very much useful as it indicates that an analytical relation exists among variables, the values are ranging from 0.548 (Inspiring Organizational Challenges - Effective decision making) to 0.812 (Teamwork - Individual learning & training). But the forthcoming values of independent variables to the dependent variable is more than 0.651 for each that provides a clarity of correlation contribution of each to the dependent variable. (Table-3)

7.5 Model Summary

Table -4

Model Summary									
<i>Model</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R Square</i>	<i>Adjusted R Square</i>	<i>Std. Error of the Estimate</i>	<i>Change Statistics</i>				
					<i>R Square Change</i>	<i>F Change</i>	<i>df1</i>	<i>df2</i>	<i>Sig. F Change</i>
1	0.871	0.758	0.753	0.49721336	0.758	134.217	4	171	0.000

Overall fitness (significance level 0.000) of the model has been found as a good perceived value of the research hypothesis; where by the adjusted R² is around 75% and suggests that the inclusive (independent) variables (TQP, ILT, IOC & EDM) are of the keen value determinants to the dependent variable of teamwork and organizations are trying to indulge all those as per their needs analysis and resources strength to better avoid the failure of the engineering projects and pilot studies. While the error term is around 25% and

proposes for the variables not been considered in this research as per the needs of engineering projects and can be part of future studies by the research fellows. (Table-4)

8. CONCLUSION

It was made an objective of the study to sum up all teamwork outcomes and suggest for better outcome options to working teams around, to commit the work as per the significance of the factor(s). It is to the recognition and acknowledgement of the statistical values of the outcome dimensions (independent variables) have been found a good growing array for the engineering firms to invest in the resources, as per their need and willingness to the organizational values that either it is going for quality dimensions, employee learning and work growth, to get prepared for the upcoming challenges of innovation or else may be to come up with the effective decision choices.

Hereby, the entire Hypothesis formed were found true (as per the results of Pearson Correlation Table-3) and accepted in order to prescribe the priorities of business and project lines to bond the individuals; Showing that *H2* is at first (81%), *H1* is at second (78%), *H3* is at third (74%) and *H4* is at fourth (65%), being lowest in correlation bound value to the dependent variable.

9. LIMITATIONS

The research is a short time study, involving low sample size as per the requirement of course work completion, from employment force having *Engineering background* working in discrete projects, about the outcome dimensions were considered from Khairpur Mirs city and its surrounding in Sindh, Pakistan.

10. FUTURE DIRECTIONS

Future study can be made in different sectors individually or comparatively to come up with the differences in forming the teams to better describe the outcome dimensions, so that a good portfolio can be invested in the same resource to build the competence in teamwork and its outcome.

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